

Causes of Thrombocytopenia in Patients above 50 Years and Distinguishing Chronic Idiopathic Thrombocytopenic Purpura from Refractory Thrombocytopenia of Myelodysplastic Syndrome

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Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Thrombocytopenia is a problem commonly encountered in the elderly with a variety of etiology. Causes of thrombocytopenia is not well studied in the elderly. Both Chronic Idiopathic Thrombocytopenic purpura and Myelodysplastic syndrome are two hematological conditions that can present as chronic persistent thrombocytopenia. Both these entities have different prognosis, predictive survival and treatment. The objective of this study was to find the causes of thrombocytopenia in patients above 50 years and to distinguish Chronic Idiopathic Thrombocytopenic purpura from Refractory thrombocytopenia of Myelodysplastic syndrome in patients coming to Department of Clinical Pathology, Govt. Medical College Kozhikode during the study period.

Materials and Methods: In this descriptive observational prospective study, a total of 150 cases of thrombocytopenia coming to clinical pathology department were selected by simple random sampling. Study group was patients above 50 years. Study period is from January 2017 to September 2018. Morphological study of peripheral smear, Bone marrow aspirate, imprint, and trephine biopsy was done in these patients. Special stains PAS and Perls were done, on marrow aspirate IHC for CD34 on bone marrow Trephine to look for increase in blasts in Myelodysplastic syndrome.

Results: The most common cause of thrombocytopenia in this study was infections 35(23%) followed by Chronic persistent thrombocytopenia, Acute Leukemia and Megaloblastic Anemia. The commonest infections were Dengue fever, Leptospirosis, Sepsis, etc. On follow up there were 28 cases of Chronic Persistent Thrombocytopenia. Out of these there were 20 cases of Chronic ITP where thrombocytopenia persisted and 8 cases which can be either Chronic ITP or MDS. Micromegakaryocytes was observed in 13 cases (65%) of Chronic ITP compared to Chronic ITP/MDS (p value 0.06). Megakaryocyte proliferation was observed in 10 (50%) cases of Chronic ITP compared to cases of Chronic ITP/MDS.

Conclusion and Limitation: From this study it was found that the most common cause of thrombocytopenia above 50 years was infections. Both ITP and MDS can cause morphological alterations in the megakaryocytes. In true cases of ITP, majority of megakaryocytes are micro or hypolobated forms, whereas in MDS, majority are normally lobated and hypolobated forms. A better distinction is possible only with a long follow up and cytogenetic study.

Keywords: Thrombocytopenia, Megakaryocyte, Chronic ITP, MDS.

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Introduction

Thrombocytopenia is a problem commonly encountered in the elderly. In some cases, a low platelet count could be the only hematological anomaly at presentation. Thrombocytopenia can result from decreased platelet production as occurs in aplastic anemia and various conditions causing bone marrow suppression, or increased platelet consumption as occurs in Immune thrombocytopenia or due to peripheral sequestration of platelets as occurs in

hypersplenism. Adult platelet counts typically vary from 150,000 to 450,000/microL, with mean values for males and females being 266,000 and 237,000/microL, respectively. [1] Thrombocytopenia in adults is characterized by a platelet count of fewer than 150×10^3 per μL . If platelet counts have remained constant for more than six months, values between 100 and $150 \times 10^3/\text{L}$ may not necessarily indicate illness. [2] Using a threshold value of $100 \times 10^3/\text{L}$ to

characterize thrombocytopenia would be suitable in identifying a pathological state. Platelet counts in seemingly healthy individuals typically range from 100 to 150 × 10⁹/L. The etiology of thrombocytopenia in the elderly population has not been well investigated. [3,4] Immune thrombocytopenic purpura, or ITP, is the most frequent cause of thrombocytopenia in children. [5] Platelet-specific autoantibodies that attach to autologous platelets are the origin of the ITP syndrome. The autologous platelets are quickly removed from the bloodstream by the mononuclear phagocyte system through macrophage Fcγ receptors, which are mostly found in the liver and spleen. [6] Treating idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura in older patients requires a different approach than in younger patients because of the increased risk of bleeding and thrombosis, the existence of comorbidities, the potential for cognitive decline or short life expectancy, and the need to manage concurrent medications like anticoagulant and antiplatelet therapy. [4] In a series of studies by Yves Najean AND Thomas Lecompte involving 276 patients 50 years of age or older, 44 of them had isolated thrombocytopenia without any other comorbidity, 196 had platelet hyper destruction (idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura [ITP]), and 44 had secondary thrombocytopenia (leukemia, cancer, chemotherapy or radiotherapy, and liver disease). Sixteen individuals had myelodysplastic syndrome, granulocytopenia, dysmyelopoiesis, and the emergence of circulating blast cells during the course of the next two to ten years. Three of them died due to acute myeloblastic leukemia. [7]

The majority of cases of acute ITP, which is thrombocytopenia lasting less than six months usually affects children and resolves spontaneously. The majority of cases of chronic ITP, which lasts longer than six months and necessitates treatment to ameliorate thrombocytopenia, involve adults. The median age of persons with chronic ITP is often between 40 and 45 years old. ITP prevalence rises with age and throughout time, with a greater incidence in women. [8] In ITP, the megakaryocytes in the bone marrow are often the only cells that show morphological change. Megakaryocytes shows increase in number with immature forms. Hypolobated and micromegakaryocytes are frequently seen with "Smooth" forms, which have a single nucleus, little cytoplasm, and a small number of granules. [9] Myelodysplastic syndromes are a major cause of thrombocytopenia in the elderly, similar to Chronic ITP. Myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS) is an age-related illness. Peripheral blood cytopenias and morphologic signs of dysplasia in bone marrow hematopoietic cellular components characterize these group of hematopoietic stem cell diseases. [9]

Refractory thrombocytopenia is a kind of refractory cytopenia that is associated with myelodysplastic syndromes. Refractory thrombocytopenia caused by MDS may be mistaken for idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura due to the possibility of megakaryocytic hyperplasia and the difficulty in distinguishing dysmegakaryopoiesis when it presents as an isolated cytopenia. There might be an increase or reduction in megakaryocytes. None of the other myeloid cell lines exhibit dysplasia (<10%) in any meaningful way. Studies using cytogenetics might be very helpful in this. [10]

Materials and Methods

Study Design: Descriptive –Observational-Prospective-study, involving patients above 50 years.

Study Group: Patients above 50 years with thrombocytopenia reaching at Department of Clinical Pathology at Calicut Medical College.

Study Setting: Study was conducted in Department of Pathology Government Medical College Calicut.

Study Period: January 2016 to September 2018.

- Patients were included in the study after getting informed written consent in native language.
- Samples for hematological investigation were received in the Department of Pathology as part of routine investigation during the period.
- All patients above 50 years diagnosed with thrombocytopenia by a complete blood count coming to the hematology Department for peripheral smear or peripheral smear with bone marrow examination were included in the study.
- A total of 150 samples was included in the study.

The following details were recorded in a Standard Performa

- a) Detailed history to rule out causes of secondary thrombocytopenia.
- b) Clinical examination findings to look for organomegaly.
- c) Complete hemogram values as obtained in an Automated Hematology Analyzer.
- d) Morphological study of peripheral blood film, bone marrow aspirate, imprint and trephine biopsy of patients with chronic Persistent thrombocytopenia.
- e) Relevant investigations if any were included.

- These patients were followed after a six month to one year period from the diagnosis of thrombocytopenia and they were reevaluated by doing a complete blood count and peripheral smear.
- Patients with Thrombocytopenia lasting more than or equal to months were categorized as Chronic Persistent Thrombocytopenia.
- These patients were categorized as Chronic ITP and MDS based on features stated below
- f) Features used to distinguish chronic ITP and MDS includes: Reference^[11]

1) Evidence of dysplasia in peripheral blood or bone marrow

2) Appearance of blasts in peripheral blood

3) Development of additional cytopenias on follow up

Patients with the above features were taken as MDS

4) Patients with platelet count reverting to normal during follow up were taken as chronic ITP

- Methods for morphological study will include
 1. Leishman stain of peripheral blood, bone marrow aspirate and imprint
 2. The blocks of trephine biopsies were cut at 5 micrometers, 2 sections were taken.
 3. One for Hematoxylin & Eosin stain and one unstained for doing CD34immunohistochemistry
 4. The H&E slides of cases with Chronic Persistent thrombocytopenia were studied. Features of Dysmegakaryopoiesis like presence of hypolobated forms, micromegakaryocytes, megakaryocyte proliferation in bone marrow trephine biopsy were studied.
 5. Special stains PAS and Perls on bone marrow aspirate to look for dyserythropoiesis and ring sideroblasts (a characteristic feature of MDS).
 6. IHC for CD34 on bone marrow trephine biopsy in cases of Chronic Persistent Thrombocytopenia.

Cells morphologically consistent with blast are counted. Clusters of blasts away from bone trabeculae that is Abnormal Localization of Immature precursors are counted.

- Thrombocytopenia was taken as platelet count of less than 1 lakh/microL, [3]
- Megakaryocytes proliferation were taken as more than 2 cells per high power field
- A hemoglobin of less than 10g/dl is taken to define anemia of MDS and neutropenia was taken as a neutrophil count less than 1.8×10^9 /L. [10]

Chronic persistent Thrombocytopenia was taken to be those cases of thrombocytopenia lasting more than 6 months. [9]

Inclusion Criteria

All patients above 50 years with Thrombocytopenia sent to our laboratory for peripheral smear examination

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with thrombocytopenia who do not come for follow up after 6 months and who do not have an accompanying bone marrow sample. This is taken to satisfy objective 2.
- Patients who do not give consent for participating in the study

Statistical Method Applied

Sample Size: Taking prevalence as 40% [12]

By applying the formula

$$N = \frac{4pq}{d^2}$$

$$P = \text{prevalence} = 40$$

$$q = (100 - P) = 60$$

$$d = 20\% \text{ of } P = 8, N = 150$$

- 150 cases were compiled and analyzed.
- Microsoft Excel and has been given in the Annexure. Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS 18.0 for windows.

Sample size = 150

Crosstabs Procedure

A range of tests and measures of association are available for two-way tables, and the cross tabs process creates both multiway and two-way tables. Which test or metric to apply depends on the table's structure and whether the categories are sorted. Measures of association and crosstab statistics are calculated for two way tables only

The study was approved by institutional Ethics committee.

Results

In this study, spanning from January 2016 to September 2018, 150 cases of thrombocytopenia in patients above 50 years coming to the department of Clinical Pathology Kozhikode medical college was included in the study. Out of these there were 28 cases of Chronic Persistent Thrombocytopenia. Out of these there were 20 cases of Chronic ITP (platelet count reverted to normal on follow up) and 8 cases which can be either Chronic ITP or MDS (thrombocytopenia persisted on follow up). Majority of the patients belong to the age group 60-69 years, which includes young old age Group.

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Median
Age	50	88	63.69	9.249	63

The study population's average age group was 63 years old.

Table 1: Mean platelet count (Total 150 cases)

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median	SD
Platelet count	2000	100000	52026.67	57000	28127.93

The mean platelet count of 150 cases is 52026.67/cmm of blood.

Figure 1: Distribution of cases based on severity of thrombocytopenia

Majority of patients presented with moderate thrombocytopenia. Out of 150 cases 50 patients had a history of fever (33.3%). 25 cases (16.7%) had Hepatosplenomegaly, 43(28.7%) patients had bleeding manifestation:

Table 2: Complete blood count findings in 150 cases

Thrombocytopenia with anemia	47(31%)
Thrombocytopenia with leukopenia	15(10%)
Thrombocytopenia with anemia and leucopenia	40 (26%)
Thrombocytopenia alone	48(32%)

Majority of cases presented with thrombocytopenia alone.

Table 3: Causes of thrombocytopenia

Causes of Thrombocytopenia	No. of Cases (%) Total Cases= 150
Infections	35(23.3%)
Chronic persistent thrombocytopenia (Chronic ITP/ MDS)	28 (18.6%)
Acute Leukemia	16(10%)
Acute ITP	14(9%)
Chronic Liver disease	8 (5.3%)
Drug induced	13(8.6%)
Megaloblastic Anemia	15(10%)
MDS(already diagnosed)	4 (2.6%)
Multiple myeloma	2 (1.3%)
SLE	2 (1.3%)
Hemolytic Anemia	2 (1.3%)
Aplastic Anemia	7 (4.6%)
DIC	2 (1.3%)
Malignancy	2(1.3%)

Table 4: Distribution of cases based on infectious etiology

Infections	No. of Cases (%) Total no. of case =35(out of 150)
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Dengue fever	10(28%)
Leptospirosis	4(11%)
Other infections	21 (60%)

Other infections include sepsis 6(17%), HIV 3 (8%), Viral fever other than Dengue 12 (31%).

Table 5: Mean platelet count in Disease groups

Causes of Thrombocytopenia	Mean Platelet Count (No. of Cases)
Dengue fever	66200 (10)
Leptospirosis	51400 (5)
Other infections	44100 (20)
Chronic persistent thrombocytopenia	53250 (28)
Acute leukemia	33187 (16)
Megaloblastic anemia	58266 (15)
Acute ITP	20071 (14)
Drug induced	64615(13)

Mean platelet count was lower in Acute ITP compared to other groups. Acute leukemia, infections, and persistent thrombocytopenia were the three most prevalent causes of thrombocytopenia out of 150 cases, accounting for 35 cases (23%) of the condition.

Among 150 patients, there were 28 cases of chronic persistent thrombocytopenia of > 6 months duration.

20 cases reverted to a normal platelet count on follow up for a period of 1 year. These cases are expected to be cases of Chronic ITP. Rest 8 cases could be either MDS or Chronic ITP. These 8 cases can be proven to be either of both at the end of a longer follow up period and cytogenetic study.

Table 6: Complete Blood Count Findings of 28 cases of Chronic Persistent Thrombocytopenia

Cytopenia	Chronic ITP No. of Cases =20	Chronic ITP/MDS No. of Cases=8
Anemia with Thrombocytopenia	9(45%)	6(75%)
Leucopenia with Thrombocytopenia	1(5%)	0
Anemia +Leucopenia+ Thrombocytopenia	1(5%)	1(12.5%)
Thrombocytopenia alone	9(45%)	1(12.5%)

Anemia was mild. Leucopenia was mild close to lower limit of normal.

Table 7: Megakaryocyte morphology in 28 cases of Chronic Persistent Thrombocytopenia

Megakaryocyte Morphology	Chronic ITP No. of cases=20	Chronic ITP/MDS No. of cases =8	P value
NormalMK forms	18 (90%)	5 (62.5%)	0.4
Hypolobated forms	12 (60%)	4 (50%)	0.4
Micro megakaryocytes	13 (65%)	2 (25%)	0.06
Single lobed nuclei	4 (20%)	1 (12.5%)	0.6
Perinuclear halo	9(45%)	2(25%)	0.2
Megakaryocyte Proliferation	10 (50%)	2(25%)	0.6
Hypolobated + micromegakaryocyte	12(60%)	2(25%)	0.2
MK proliferation +hypolobated + micromegakaryocyte	10 (50%)	2(25%)	0.4

Megakaryocyte proliferation and hypolobated forms are more seen in cases of chronic ITP. IHC for CD 34 was negative in both cases of Chronic ITP and Chronic ITP/MDS. There were no increase in blasts or abnormal localization of immature precursors.

PAS and Perls stain were negative for Dyserythropoiesis and Ring Sideroblasts in cases with Chronic Persistent Thrombocytopenia.

Figure 2: Peripheral Smear showing Thrombocytopenia in a case of chronic ITP

Figure 3: Micromegakaryocytes in Bone Marrow Trepine biopsy in Chronic ITP (H&E stain)

Figure 4: Hypolobated megakaryocytes in bone marrow trephine biopsy in Chronic ITP

Discussion

Similar to the findings of Choudhary et al., 84 cases (56%) of the 150 instances of thrombocytopenia were little female patients, and 66 cases (44%) were male. [13] Another research by Biino G et al. discovered that women had more platelets than males in the age range of 15–64 years and above 64 years, but there was no difference in the platelet count of men and women before the age of 15. [14] However, it is unknown why this is the case. A plausible explanation for this might be the decrease in body iron levels in females, which happens during menstruation and may continue into old age, hence inducing platelet production. [15] But after puberty, the hormonal variations between men and women could potentially be important. [16] Elderly persons often have immunological thrombocytopenia (ITP) due to their extended life expectancy. ITP diagnosis is difficult in elderly due to the possibility of an underlying myelodysplastic condition. There aren't many studies on older persons, and the majority of therapy recommendations are dependent on professional judgment. Compared to younger patients, this patient population has different treatment needs, and considerations include higher risk of bleeding and thrombosis, comorbidities, potential cognitive decline or short life expectancy, and concurrent medications like anticoagulant and antiplatelet therapy. [4] In older patients, intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIg) therapy and steroids continue to be the first-line therapies; however, extended steroid treatment should be avoided, and IVIg therapy may result in renal failure. Compared to younger individuals, splenectomy is less effective and has a higher risk of thrombosis in

elderly. Additionally, severe co-morbidities may rule out surgery. As a result, other second-line therapies are usually used. For milder ITP, dapsone and danazol may be an alternative.

The age range of 61–70 years had the highest prevalence of thrombocytopenia (38%, 58 cases), followed by the 50–60 age group (34%, 52 cases). The age-related decrease in platelet count might be the cause of this. [15] ITP prevalence rises with age and throughout time, with a greater incidence in women. [10] A bigger research by Biino et al. also discovered a link between age and platelet count, finding that a 10-year rise in age was accompanied by a $9 \times 10^9/L$ drop in platelet count. [14] Additionally, Biino et al. discovered that, in comparison to early infancy, the platelet count decreased by 25% in women and by 35% in males as they aged. [14] The lower life expectancy after 70 years of age may be the cause of the decreased incidence of thrombocytopenia above that age.

The mean platelet count in patients with bleeding manifestation was 26604 which showed a statistically significant correlation ($P < 0.05$) which was in concordance with study conducted by Lynne uhl et al. [17]

The most common cause of thrombocytopenia was infections 35 (23%) followed by Chronic persistent thrombocytopenia, Acute Leukemia and Megaloblastic Anemia. The commonest infections were Dengue fever, Leptospirosis, Sepsis, Other viral fevers, HIV etc. According to a research by Choudhary et al. involving all age groups, megaloblastic anemia was the most frequent cause of thrombocytopenia, followed by ITP and acute leukemia. [13]

Viral Fever Induced Thrombocytopenia

Viral infections frequently result in thrombocytopenia. Viral-mediated thrombocytopenia varies throughout viral infections and is frequently complex. When the dengue virus infects hematopoietic progenitor cells, it suppresses megakaryopoiesis. This leads to an indirect decrease in platelet formation, which is caused by changed cytokine levels in the bone marrow as a result of reduced stromal cell activity. [18]

The pathophysiology of thrombocytopenia may be aided by the activation, mitochondrial malfunction, and increased apoptosis observed in platelets from dengue infected patients. [19]

Drug induced thrombocytopenia was seen in 13 (8.6%) of the cases. The drugs which caused thrombocytopenia were chemotherapeutic (3 cases), Bortezomib induced (3 cases) for treating multiple myeloma, antiplatelet (4 cases), Imatinib induced (2) used in treatment of Chronic Myeloid Leukemia, Azathioprine (1 case) for Crohn's disease, Methotrexate (1 case).

Heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT) is a classic example of a drug-induced thrombocytopenia. It is the most frequent reason why thrombocytopenia linked to drugs occurs. [20] Antibodies produced by drugs can interact with platelets by activating complement or non-complement. Drugs commonly associated with thrombocytopenia are quinidine, quinine, rifampin, trimethoprim, digoxin etc. [21]

Chronic thrombocytopenia following cytotoxic chemotherapy are seen as a result of marrow injury. [21]

Thrombocytopenia in Chronic Liver disease

The most frequent hematological abnormality seen in individuals with chronic liver disease (CLD) is thrombocytopenia. [22] Up to 35% of individuals having bone marrow biopsies for thrombocytopenia with no known cause also had cirrhosis. [23] Thrombocytopenia is not just a sign of advanced illness but also has a negative prognosis in patients with chronic liver disease (CLD). Patients with thrombocytopenia sometimes cannot receive important treatments like medication or invasive diagnostic or therapeutic procedures.

Thrombocytopenia in Megaloblastic and Aplastic Anemia

Thrombocytopenia in megaloblastic anemia can be caused by a variety of factors, including decreased platelet destruction, inefficient thrombopoiesis, and marrow hypoplasia, which results in fewer megakaryocytes. In certain research, hypo production has been suggested as the reason of thrombocytopenia in megaloblastic anemia, whereas ineffi-

cient thrombopoiesis has been suggested as the explanation in other studies. [24]

Among 150 patients, who presented with thrombocytopenia 28 patients had chronic persistent thrombocytopenia lasting beyond 6 months. 20 of them reverted to a normal platelet count during follow up for a period of one year. The probable cause of thrombocytopenia in these patients may be an immune mediated mechanism probably a chronic ITP. "Persistent" ITP is defined as having low platelet counts for at least three but fewer than twelve months following diagnosis. ITP. [25]

The rest 8 cases could be either MDS or Chronic ITP, since Chronic ITP can last for months and years. There were no additional cytopenias, appearance of blasts or evidence of dysplasia in the peripheral blood and bone marrow in the remaining 8 cases. These 8 cases whether ITP or MDS can be proven better at the end of a longer follow up period and cytogenetic study.

Myelodysplastic Syndrome

Cytopenia and dysplasia in one or more of the major myeloid lineages characterize the myelodysplastic syndromes, a group of clonal hematopoietic stem cell disorders. The cytopenias are caused in part by the apoptosis of bone marrow progenitors. To diagnose MDS, cytopenia in at least one hematopoietic lineage is necessary. The suggested cut off points for all MDS cytopenias include platelet count <1 lakh, absolute neutrophil count <1800/cmm, and hemoglobin <10g/dl. [10]

Diagnosis of MDS: bone marrow and peripheral smear are crucial in the diagnosis of MDS. Further details on the distribution and percentage of blasts inside the marrow space can be obtained with a bone marrow trephine biopsy. In most cases, the bone marrow in MDS patients is hyper cellular; less frequently, it is normocellular or hypo cellular for age. [10]

Role of CD 34 in the diagnosis of MDS

An antigen expressed on the blasts is CD 34 Utilizing CD34 in immunohistochemical analysis, one may evaluate the blast proportion in MDS patients. The ligand for CD34 is CD62L (L-selectin), which is an intercellular adhesion protein and cell surface glycoprotein found in hematopoietic progenitor cells. Although its precise role is uncertain, it mediates the attachment of hematopoietic stem cells to either stromal cells or the extracellular matrix of bone marrow.

Megakaryocytes may stain in megaloblastic anemia, however in certain instances of MDS, CD 34 is positive in megakaryocytes. [6]

Refractory Thrombocytopenia of MDS

MDS includes a category of cytopenia called as Refractory Thrombocytopenia. This category of MDS with single lineage dysplasia encompasses the MDS cases that present with unexplained thrombocytopenia with more than or equal to 10% dysplastic megakaryocytes of at least 30 megakaryocytes evaluated. An uncommon variant of myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS) known as refractory thrombocytopenia (RTC) first manifests as persistent pure thrombocytopenia. RTC has frequently been misinterpreted as idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura because to the absence of discernible dysplasia. [26]

Myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS) should not be the diagnosis for individuals who have isolated thrombocytopenia without substantial dysplasia; instead, idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP) should be investigated. Correct diagnosis is crucial since MDS and ITP require distinct courses of therapy. Numerous investigations revealed that individuals with cytogenetic abnormalities ultimately received a diagnosis of ITP. [27]

The most consistent and dependable characteristics of megakaryocyte dysplasia include hypolobated bi-nucleate, multinucleate, and micromegakaryocytes.

Immune Thrombocytopenia in Adults

The majority of cases of chronic ITP, which lasts longer than six months and necessitates treatment to ameliorate thrombocytopenia, involve adults. The median age of people with chronic ITP is often between 40 and 45 years old; however, in a sizable patient series, 74% of 934 cases (with a range of 16 to 87 years old) were younger than 40 years old. [22] ITP is an exclusionary diagnosis. [28] Based on a peripheral thrombocytopenia demonstration, together with a physical examination, history, and full blood work to exclude out concomitant conditions.

Among the 20 cases which presented as chronic ITP, peripheral smear showed presence of polychromatic RBCs in 7 of the cases. This may be secondary to blood loss in ITP. Bone marrow examination in 20 cases of Chronic ITP showed the presence of micromegakaryocyte in 13 cases (65%) compared to MDS, even though statistically not significant. They are the outcome of both the presence of numerous juvenile forms and noticeably increased platelet production. In 95.3% of the ITP patients, Muhury M et al. and JubelilerSJ et al. also discovered an elevated megakaryocyte count. [23]

Out of 20 cases of Chronic ITP megakaryocyte proliferation was found in 10 (50%) of cases. This could be because immune-mediated platelet destruction in the spleen and other reticuloendothelial tissues stimulates bone marrow

megakaryocytes, increasing the rate at which platelets are synthesized. JubelilerSJ et al. and Muhury M et al. similarly discovered elevated megakaryocyte counts in 95.3% of ITP patients. [2] However in this study no association was found (p value=0.6).

Compared to chronic ITP, in the remaining 8 case which was expected to be of MDS, most common finding in the bone marrow was presence of hypolobated forms. Hypolobated megakaryocytes are a morphological feature of dysplasia. They constitute megakaryocytes with defective nuclear development and the inability to properly undergo differentiation. But they can still be seen in ITP and Megaloblastic Anemia.

IHC for CD34 showed no increase in blasts or ALIP (Abnormal Localization of Immature Precursors) in these 8 cases suspected to be of Chronic ITP/MDS. Perinuclear halo doesn't seem to be a finding of significance. It is seen in ITP, megaloblastic anemia and MDS.

Hypolobated and Micromegakaryocytes can be seen in both ITP and MDS. Both ITP and MDS can present as isolated chronic persistent thrombocytopenia.

Better distinction between them is possible only after a longer follow up period large sample size and cytogenetic studies. Cytogenetic studies may be of considerable aid in this distinction. [29]

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